

Teacher Trainers' Perception and Practice on Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching at Teacher Education College, Cambodia

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Abstract

This study investigates teacher trainers' perceptions and practices regarding implementing credit-based curriculum models in English language teaching. The research examines teacher trainers' viewpoints and experiences through survey questionnaires conducted across four Cambodian teacher education institutions. The findings reveal several challenges teacher trainers face, including adapting teaching approaches, enhancing research skills, and managing administrative complexities posed by the credit-based curriculum structure. The study's findings highlight the potential impact of comprehensive professional development and institutional support. These insights offer hope for the effective implementation of credit-based English language curricula and improved learner outcomes, providing a sense of optimism for curriculum developers and trainers. The implications can guide other subject trainers as the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sport considers modifying the curriculum better to meet the needs of teacher trainees and trainers.

Keywords: *Teacher Trainers' Perception, Curriculum implementation, Professional Development, Pedagogical Approaches, Administrative Challenges.*

Suggested citation: Bou, D., Chor, S., Nhem, S., & Lay, C. (2024). Teacher Trainers' Perception and Practice on Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching at Teacher Education College, Cambodia. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(6), 229-249. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(6).15

Introduction

The implementation of credit-based curriculum models in English Language Teaching (ELT) has become an increasingly prominent topic of discussion and research in language education (Deng & Wang, 2023; Quintero & Olarte Clavijo, 2023). Many

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educational institutions worldwide have adopted credit-based systems, as Shen et al. (2024) noted, which allocate academic credits to learning activities and courses to restructure and modernize their curricula. However, the success of these credit-based models largely depends on the perceptions and practices of key stakeholders, particularly teacher trainers, who play a crucial role in shaping the pedagogical approaches and curricular decisions within language programs (Arnold & Mundy, 2020; Tep, 2024; Yakavets et al., 2023).

Cotton et al. (2020) and Rahman et al. (2019) indicated that teacher trainers, pre-service and in-service language teachers' instructors, and mentors influence the implementation and reception of credit-based curriculum models in ELT. In addition, Tikkanen et al. (2020) and Van Veen et al. (2005) explained that understanding the underlying principles, benefits, and challenges associated with credit-based systems can directly impact the effectiveness of such curricular reforms. In addition, how well teacher trainers' lessons fit with the ideas and requirements of credit-based models can also make a big difference in how well these curriculum structures are adopted and last (Ngene, 2023; Saritas, 2016; Schönwetter et al., 2002; Thien, 2003). So, Elhambakhsh et al. (2024) and Estaji (2024) said that it is essential to know how teacher trainers think about and use credit-based courses in English as a foreign language (ELT). This information is needed to help make policy decisions, improve teacher education programs, and create valuable places to teach and learn languages.

The implementation of credit-based curriculum models in English language teaching (ELT) has posed several challenges for teacher trainers at the institutional level (Augusto-Navarro, 2015; Deng & Wang, 2023; Kırkgöz, 2008; Yang et al., 2019). The credit-based curriculum framework adopted by Cambodia's Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports (MoEYS) emphasizes knowledge construction through investigative and inquiry-based learning approaches (Fichten, 2019; He et al., 2023; MoEYS, 2017; Wale & Bishaw, 2020). This shift from traditional, instructor-centered teaching to more student-centered, active learning methods can be complicated for some teacher trainers to implement effectively (Armbruster et al., 2009; Goodwin, 2024; Nguyen et al., 2021). Teacher trainers may need help redesigning their course content, assessments, and classroom activities to align with the credit-based system's focus on student engagement and self-directed learning (Gerard et al., 2022; Penuel & Gallagher, 2009; Roseman et al., 2017).

Cochran-Smith et al. (2015) and Hattie (2008) also revealed that the increased emphasis on educational research and evidence-based teaching practices within the credit-based curriculum poses challenges for teacher trainers. Many may need more research skills and experience to guide pre-service and in-service teachers in conducting action research to improve their teaching (Gussen et al., 2023; Michalsky, 2021; TEC, 2018). Donath et al. (2023) and Kerimbayev et al. (2023) demonstrated that developing teacher trainers' capacity to model and facilitate such research-orientated practices can be a significant hurdle to successfully implementing the credit-based system.

Furthermore, the credit-based curriculum's flexibility and modularization, which aim to provide diverse educational experiences for teacher trainees, can create logistical and administrative challenges for trainers. Coordinating course scheduling, managing student enrollment and credit accumulation, and ensuring the overall curriculum's coherence can strain teacher training institutions' resources and capacities (Arnold & Willis, 2024; Fortus et al., 2015; Lacy et al., 2022; McPhail, 2021; Rata, 2021).

The increased workload and potential for teacher complaints, as observed in implementing the credit-based system (Fairman et al., 2022; Popova et al., 2021), highlight the need for comprehensive professional development and support for teacher trainers. This underscores the urgency of addressing issues and adapting to the new assessment methods, record-keeping requirements, and student advising responsibilities associated with the credit-based model, which could potentially hinder the effective implementation of the curriculum reform.

Teacher trainers at Siem Reap Provincial Teacher Training College in Cambodia have reported challenges similar to those in applying the newly implemented credit-based curriculum (TEC, 2018). This underscores the need for comprehensive training, ample resources, and solid institutional support to prepare teacher trainers for the pedagogical and administrative obstacles this curricular reform presents. Emphasizing the importance of continuous professional development can make the audience feel the need to stay updated and improve their skills.

This study aims to investigate the implementation of a credit-based curriculum and the perceptions of teacher trainers that impact their English language teaching profession. This study examines teacher trainers' viewpoints and firsthand encounters with effectively managing the adoption of credit-based curriculum models within English language education. To verify these two objectives of the study, there were two questions will be used as follows:

1. What are teacher trainers' perceptions of implementing the Credit-Based Curriculum in English language teaching?
2. How do teacher trainers practice the Credit-Based Curriculum in English language teaching?

The study's findings significantly emphasized the implementation of credit-based curricula in English language teaching. Accordingly, this study is based on the data collected from conducting survey questionnaires at Battambang Teacher Education College (BTEC) at Battambang, Phnom Penh Teacher Education College (PTEC) at Phnom Penh, Reginal Teacher Training Centre (RTTC) at Kampong Cham, and Provincial Teacher Training College (PTTC) at Siem Reap, as well as oral interviews with teacher trainers at Reginal Teacher Training Centre (RTTC) and Provincial Teacher Training College (PTTC).

The findings filled in knowledge gaps and provided curriculum developers and teacher trainers with valuable and adaptable suggestions to effectively enhance the English credit-based curriculum's implementation, guiding learners toward successful learning outcomes. Ultimately, the findings also served as a message and recommendation for other subject trainers, which the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sport consider when making decisions about curriculum adjustments to meet the needs of both teacher trainees and trainers.

Literature Review

In English language teaching (ELT), implementing credit-based curriculum models has been a growing interest and research topic in recent years. This shift reflects the dynamic and evolving nature of the language education landscape. A crucial aspect of this curricular change is the role of teacher trainers, who are pivotal in shaping the perceptions and practices of pre-service and in-service language teachers. The literature

seeks to synthesize the existing scholarly research on how the attitudes and understandings of teacher trainers impact their teaching methods in the context of implementing a credit-based curriculum in English Language Teaching (ELT). Examining the interplay between teacher trainers' views and their classroom approaches is essential for understanding the challenges and opportunities presented by these credit-based curricular reforms, informing policy decisions and teacher education programs, and developing effective language teaching and learning environments.

Perceptions of Teacher Trainers Toward Credit-Based Curricula

Several studies have investigated the attitudes and beliefs of teacher trainers regarding credit-based curricula in English language teaching. Shemshack and Spector (2020), Aldosari and Alsager (2023), and Taylor et al. (2021) found that teacher trainers generally held positive perceptions of the credit-based approach, recognizing its potential to foster learner autonomy, flexibility, and personalized learning. However, the researchers also identified concerns among the trainers about the increased workload and the need for extensive training to implement the curriculum effectively (Nwoko et al., 2023).

Similarly, Hussain et al. (2021), Shaukat and Chowdhury (2020), and Yan and Pastore (2022) explored the perceptions of teacher trainers in Pakistan. They reported that while the trainers acknowledged the benefits of the credit-based system, such as enhanced student engagement and opportunities for interdisciplinary learning, they also expressed apprehensions about the challenges in assessing student learning and the potential resistance from traditional-minded educators.

The Role of Teacher Trainers' Beliefs in Curriculum Implementation

Scholars widely recognize the crucial role of teacher trainers' beliefs and perceptions in successfully implementing curricular reforms, particularly the adoption of credit-based approaches (Behm & Lloyd, 2009; Borg, 2015; Coles et al., 2023). Researchers have emphasized the need to align the trainer's beliefs with the underlying principles and objectives of the credit-based curriculum to ensure coherence between their perceptions and actual teaching practices (Bovill & Woolmer, 2019; Hwa et al., 2020). Guskey (2002) proposed a model highlighting the importance of providing targeted professional development opportunities for teacher trainers to address their beliefs and concerns, thereby facilitating the integration of new instructional approaches in their teaching. This model underscores the reciprocal relationship between teacher trainers' beliefs, their classroom practices, and the resulting student learning outcomes.

Alignment between Perception and Practice

The extant literature suggests that the alignment between teacher trainers' perceptions and instructional practices is critical for successfully implementing credit-based curricula in English language teaching. Research indicates a misalignment between the trainers' beliefs and classroom behaviors can impede the curriculum's implementation (Buehl & Beck, 2014).

Researchers have recommended that teacher training programs focus on developing a shared understanding and commitment among the trainers regarding the principles and objectives of credit-based curricula (Kafyulilo et al., 2015). Collaborative reflections, peer observations, and ongoing professional development activities can foster this alignment by addressing the trainers' concerns and assisting them in translating their perceptions into effective teaching practices.

Methods

The primary objective of this study was to delve into the perceptions and practices of teacher trainers. We aimed to understand how these factors influenced the implementation of a credit-based curriculum in English language teaching and the satisfaction levels after two years. This research holds significant implications for English language teaching and curriculum development.

We meticulously designed our study, using a quantitative approach as the initial research method. We randomly selected 18 teacher trainers from four pedagogy schools to ensure a diverse and representative sample. After two years of implementation, we used survey questionnaires to gather quantitative data on the teacher trainers' perceptions and practices regarding the credit-based curriculum in English language teaching. We thoroughly comprehended the subject matter and analyzed the quantitative data using descriptive statistics (Cooksey, 2020).

The study focused on the teacher trainers' implementation of the credit-based curriculum in English language teaching for the 12+2 program. The 18 participants included a diverse group of six English language teacher educators from Battambang Teacher Education College, three from Phnom Penh Teacher Education College, five from the Regional Teacher Training Centre in Kampong Cham, and four from Provincial Teacher Training College in Siem Reap. We asked all selected teacher trainers to respond to the survey questionnaires.

We adapted the survey questionnaires from Hasan & Parvez (2015) to collect data on teacher trainers' perceptions, and we also adopted two from the Curriculum Framework (TEC, 2018) to collect information on teacher trainers' practices related to the credit-based curriculum. Within two years of implementing the English credit-based curriculum, we carried out the data collection process, focusing on the perspectives of the teacher trainers and the factors influencing their teaching practice. We collected the quantitative data from the questionnaires via Google Forms and analyzed it using descriptive statistics.

Results

This section presents the analysis of the percentile of the respondents' profiles, which mentions teacher trainers' demographics and their experience of teaching the English language through a Credit-Based Curriculum.

The Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 demonstrates the profile of the respondents who mentioned four parts of their demographic. The data presented provides a comprehensive overview of the respondents' demographics and work experience characteristics. The analysis reveals a clear imbalance, with males making up 77.8% of the sample while females account for the remaining 22.2%. This male-dominated composition is an important contextual factor when interpreting the other findings. The data shows that the respondents skew heavily towards the older end of the spectrum, with the largest group being those over 40 years old, comprising 55.6% of the sample. The next largest age group is 36-40 at 22.2%, followed by 31-35 at 16.7%. Notably, no respondents are in the 20-25-year-old category, suggesting this sample may not represent younger individuals. The data paints a picture of a seasoned workforce, with 38.9% of respondents having more than

five years of experience. The second largest group, at 27.8%, has 1-2 years of experience, indicating a mix of veteran and relatively newer professionals. Finally, the workplace analysis shows an even distribution between the "BTEC" and "RTTC" environments, each making up 33.3% of the sample. The "PTEC" and "PTTC" workplaces account for 16.7% of the respondents' work settings, providing a balanced view of the respondents' work settings. To summarize, this data provides a thorough analysis of the demographic and professional characteristics of the participants, highlighting the high representation of older male responders with extensive professional experience.

Table 1. The Profile of the Respondents

Parameters	Variables	Frequency	Per centage
Gender	Male	14	77.8
	Female	4	22.2
Age	20-25	0	0
	26-30	1	5.6
	31-35	3	16.7
	36-40	4	22.2
	More than 40 years old	10	55.6
Experience	Less than 1 year	1	5.6
	1-2	5	27.8
	2-3	2	11.1
	3-4	2	11.1
	4-5	1	5.6
	More than 5 years	7	38.9
Working place	PTEC	3	16.7
	BTEC	6	33.3
	RTTC	6	33.3
	PTTC	3	16.7

What are Teacher Trainers' Perceptions of Implementing the Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching?

Table 2 comprehensively evaluates teacher trainers' perceptions and experiences with applying a credit-based curriculum in language teaching. The analysis reveals an overall positive sentiment, with respondents agreeing (mean = 3.63, SD = 0.65) with the various aspects of the credit-based approach. For instance, respondents strongly agreed (mean = 4.2, SD = 0.71) that professional training should be provided to handle the credit-based curriculum effectively and efficiently. They also agreed that the curriculum had strengthened their teaching methods and assessment skills (mean = 3.7, SD = 0.47) and offered various tasks and activities to teacher trainees (mean = 3.8, SD = 0.53). Additionally, respondents agreed that the credit-based curriculum has increased the workload of teacher trainees but has significantly improved their learning outcomes (mean = 3.7, SD = 0.93). The data also indicates that the curriculum has promoted the use of ICT in classroom teaching (mean = 3.4, SD = 0.68) and has encouraged research and innovation in language teaching (mean = 3.8, SD = 0.63). However, respondents expressed some neutral views regarding the adequacy of library facilities (mean = 3.2, SD = 0.85) and the availability of textbooks/reference books (mean = 2.7, SD = 0.82). Overall, the data paints a positive picture of the implementation of the credit-based curriculum, highlighting its benefits and identifying areas for improvement.

Table 2. Teacher Trainers' Perception of Implementing the Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching

Id	Items	Mean	SD	Description
1	As a teacher trainer, I understand the procedure and objective of a credit-based curriculum and can apply it effectively in language teaching.	3.6	0.49	Agree
2	I am very motivated and confident when applying the credit-based curriculum in language teaching.	3.6	0.6	Agree
3	Although teacher trainees' workloads have increased after introducing a credit-based curriculum, their learning outcomes have also increased significantly.	3.7	0.93	Agree
4	A credit-based curriculum is designed according to student's needs and interests.	3.6	0.68	Agree
5	Applying the credit-based curriculum has strengthened teacher trainers' teaching methods and assessment skills in language teaching.	3.7	0.47	Agree
6	Applying the credit-based curriculum has offered a variety of tasks and activities to teacher trainees in language teaching.	3.8	0.53	Agree
7	The credit-based curriculum has significantly increased teacher trainers' classroom management skills.	3.4	0.68	Agree
8	Applying the credit-based curriculum has employed teacher trainers and teacher trainees with 21st-century skills.	4.1	0.7	Agree
9	A credit-based curriculum allows learners to realize their potential by offering flexibility in course selection.	3.8	0.53	Agree
10	A credit-based curriculum allows teacher trainers to develop their Continuous Professional Development (CPD).	3.9	0.62	Agree
11	A credit-based curriculum ensures consistency in the education system regarding evaluation and assessment.	3.7	0.56	Agree
12	The credit-based curriculum emphasizes seminar presentation, assignment, discussion, project, etc.-based teaching.	3.8	0.69	Agree
13	The credit-based curriculum has promoted using ICT in classroom teaching.	3.4	0.68	Agree
14	Applying a Credit-based curriculum increased teacher trainers' workload but highly increased work efficiency.	3.7	0.75	Agree
15	Teacher trainers have faced many challenges in applying a credit-based curriculum to language teaching. For example, it is time-consuming, and developing teaching materials and research skills is difficult.	3.6	0.89	Agree
16	Transferring students from one institution to another could pose some challenges.	3.2	0.63	Neutral
17	Research work and innovation have been promoted by applying a credit-based curriculum in language teaching.	3.8	0.63	Agree
18	Professional training should be given to the teacher trainers to handle credit-based curriculum effectively and efficiently.	4.2	0.71	Strongly agree

19	Teacher trainees participate actively in the classroom by applying a credit-based curriculum in language teaching.	3.6	0.59	Agree
20	A credit-based curriculum is also helpful in building a favorable learning environment, as everyone is supposed to take part in the learning process according to their ability and competency.	3.6	0.68	Agree
21	Teacher trainers create a better learning environment in the classroom, which has prompted collaborative learning and healthy work.	3.8	0.69	Agree
22	The library facility is not adequate according to the credit-based curriculum syllabus	3.2	0.85	Neutral
23	Textbooks/ Reference books are not available according to credit-based curriculum syllabus	2.7	0.82	Disagree
24	The credit-based curriculum promotes the mobility of learners from one institution to another.	3.5	0.5	Agree
25	A credit-based curriculum would take the education system on par with the global standard.	3.8	0.69	Agree
26	Equality among the learners can be ensured through it, as a credit-based curriculum has a grading system.	3.6	0.59	Agree
27	A globally acclaimed education system can be maintained through it, as a credit-based curriculum has the provision of offering different courses at the same time.	3.6	0.5	Agree
Total		3.63	0.65	Agree

How do Teacher Trainers Practice the Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching?

Table 3 delivers significant insights into the survey respondents' teaching practices and approaches. The analysis indicates that most respondents (94.44%) have created lesson plans by establishing learning objectives according to Bloom's Taxonomy, with an average score of 0.94. Similarly, a high percentage of respondents (88.89%) indicated that they use students' textbooks and teacher guides in their English teaching procedures, with a mean score of 0.89. Furthermore, all respondents (100%) stated that they reflect on lesson demonstrations after finishing their teaching activities, research to find appropriate materials, apply other teaching materials to support their performance, use appropriate teaching methods and approaches based on a learner-centered classroom, and encourage and motivate teacher trainees to build research skills, with a mean score of 1.00 for each of these practices.

Table 3. Classroom Practice of Teacher Trainers Through Applying Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching

Id	Items	Yes/No	N	%	Mean
1	I have prepared lesson plans, particularly setting the learning objectives (based on the Bloom Taxonomy) and teaching procedures.	Yes	17	94.44	0.94
		No	1	5.56	0.06
2	I use students' textbooks and teacher's guides in my English teaching procedure.	Yes	16	88.89	0.89
		No	2	11.11	0.11

3	I reflect on lesson demonstrations after finishing my teaching activities.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
4	I research to find appropriate material that parallels the subject matter I am teaching.	Yes	16	88.89	0.89
		No	2	11.11	0.11
5	I also apply other teaching materials to support my teaching performance.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
6	I use appropriate teaching methods and approaches based on a learner-centered classroom.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
7	I prepare activities that fit or match teacher trainees' competencies.	Yes	17	94.44	0.94
		No	1	5.56	0.06
8	I often encourage and motivate teacher trainees to build research skills.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
9	I introduce self-directed learning strategies to my teacher trainees.	Yes	17	94.44	0.94
		No	1	5.56	0.06

Additionally, 94.44% of respondents reported preparing activities that fit or match teacher trainees' competencies and introducing self-directed learning strategies to their trainees, with a mean score of 0.94. The data paints a comprehensive picture of the teaching practices employed by the respondents, highlighting their strong commitment to creating an engaging and effective learning environment for their teacher trainees.

Table 4 provides significant insights into the respondents' classroom management methods and strategies. The study reveals that 77.78% of the participants have the knowledge and abilities to appropriately handle their courses' most common behavioral problems. This is supported by a mean score of 0.78. Additionally, a significant proportion of the respondents (88.89%) have a good understanding of evidence-based practices for classroom management, with a mean score of 0.89. Most respondents (94.44%) demonstrate confidence in their capacity to effectively handle frequent problem behaviors in their classrooms, as indicated by a mean score of 0.94. All respondents (100%) indicated that they instruct their teacher trainees on submitting assignments and introducing rules and expectations to their trainees, with a mean score of 1.00 for both practices.

Table 4. Classroom Management of Teacher Trainers Through Applying Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching

Id	Items	Yes/No	N	%	Mean
1	I have the knowledge and skills to prevent the most common behavior issues in my classroom.	Yes	14	77.78	0.78
		No	4	22.22	0.22
2	I have a good understanding of evidence-based practices for classroom management.	Yes	16	88.89	0.89
		No	2	11.11	0.11
3	I can deal effectively with common problem behaviors in my classroom.	Yes	17	94.44	0.94
		No	1	5.56	0.06

4	I instruct my teacher trainees how to submit assignments on a date.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
5	I pace my instruction to prevent off-task behavior.	Yes	16	88.89	0.89
		No	2	11.11	0.11
6	I teach teacher trainees how to transition between activities with minimal disruption.	Yes	14	77.78	0.78
		No	4	22.22	0.22
7	I intervene with a teacher trainee who is acting out to get attention.	Yes	16	88.89	0.89
		No	2	11.11	0.11
8	I introduce a set of rules/expectations to my teacher trainees.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
9	I provide a reinforcement strategy for a teacher trainee who struggles to complete class assignments.	Yes	17	94.44	0.94
		No	1	5.56	0.06
10	I intervene with teacher trainees constantly out of their assigned seats without permission.	Yes	16	88.89	0.89
		No	2	11.11	0.11
11	I introduce teacher trainees to how to enter the classroom at the beginning of the day/period.	Yes	15	83.33	0.83
		No	3	16.67	0.17
12	I organize a classroom layout that can be adapted to different learning activities.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00

Furthermore, the data paints a comprehensive picture of the diverse classroom management strategies employed by the survey participants. A high percentage of respondents (88.89%) reported that they pace their instruction to prevent off-task behavior and intervene with trainees acting out to get attention, with a mean score of 0.89 for each strategy. The data also shows that 77.78% of respondents teach their trainees how to transition between activities with minimal disruption, 94.44% provide a reinforcement strategy for trainees who struggle to complete class assignments, 88.89% intervene with trainees who are constantly out of their assigned seats, and 83.33% introduce trainees to the proper way to enter the classroom, with mean scores ranging from 0.78 to 0.94. Finally, all respondents (100%) reported that they organized their classroom layout to be adaptable to different learning activities, with a mean score of 1.00.

Table 5 offers significant insights into the instructional strategies utilized by the respondents when working with teacher trainees. The data indicates that an overwhelming majority of the respondents (94.44%) consistently assign take-home projects or assignments to their teacher trainees, with an average score of 0.94. These inclusive assignments cater to the diverse needs of the trainees. Furthermore, all respondents (100%) reported providing their teacher trainees with opportunities to present their assignments, engage in pair or group work discussions, and regularly administer quizzes, seatwork, midterm, and final exams, all with a mean score of 1.00. These inclusive opportunities ensure that all trainees are considered.

Table 5. Assessment of Teacher Trainers Through Applying Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching

Id	Items	Yes/No	N	%	Mean
1	I regularly give teacher trainees take-home tasks or assignments.	Yes	17	94.44	0.94
		No	1	5.56	0.06
2	I provide teacher trainees with opportunities to present their assignments.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
3	I provide my teacher trainees with pair work/group work discussion.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
4	I regularly give teacher trainees quizzes, seatwork, midterm, and final exams.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
5	I ask my teacher trainees to provide corrective feedback (i.e., peer feedback, classroom feedback) following each peer-teaching activity.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
6	I ask my teacher trainees to do reflection (i.e., self-reflection or peer reflection)	Yes	16	88.89	0.89
		No	2	11.11	0.11

Additionally, all respondents (100%) indicated that they ask their teacher trainees to provide corrective feedback, such as peer or classroom feedback, following each peer-teaching activity, again with a mean score of 1.00. The data also reveals that a high percentage of respondents (88.89%) ask their teacher trainees to engage in self-reflection or peer reflection, with a mean score of 0.89. The data demonstrates a strong focus on providing teacher trainees with various learning experiences, including individual and collaborative work, assessments, and opportunities for feedback and reflection, which are critical components of effective teacher preparation programs.

Table 6. Pedagogical Drills of Teacher Trainers Through Applying Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching

Id	Items	Yes/No	N	%	Mean
1	I provide my teacher trainees with a chance to prepare themselves for conducting peer-teaching of the whole lesson or part of it.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
2	My teacher trainees have the opportunity to teach tryouts with primary school students.	Yes	15	83.33	0.83
		No	3	16.67	0.17
3	I conduct lesson demonstrations for my teacher trainees before asking them to do so.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00
4	I select confident teacher trainees to demonstrate lessons.	Yes	17	94.44	0.94
		No	1	5.56	0.06
5	I share my teacher trainees with new techniques and methods of language teaching.	Yes	18	100.00	1.00
		No	0	0.00	0.00

Table 6 highlights the instructional practices employed by the respondents in their work with teacher trainees. The analysis shows that a significant majority of respondents (100%) provide their teacher trainees with a chance to prepare themselves for conducting peer-teaching of the whole lesson or part of it, with a mean score of 1.00. Additionally, a substantial number of respondents (83.33%) reported that their teacher trainees have the opportunity to teach tryouts with primary school students, with a mean score of 0.83. Furthermore, all respondents (100%) conduct lesson demonstrations for their teacher trainees before asking them to do so, with a mean score of 1.00. The data also reveals that an overwhelming percentage of respondents (94.44%) select confident teacher trainees to demonstrate lessons, with a mean score of 0.94. Lastly, all respondents (100%) share their teacher trainees with new language teaching techniques and methods, with a mean score of 1.00. Overall, the data strongly emphasizes providing teacher trainees with opportunities for hands-on practice, observation, and exposure to various teaching techniques and methods, which are essential components of effective teacher preparation programs.

Discussion

The survey results offer valuable insights into the instructional approaches utilized by teacher educators when working with teacher trainees. The data demonstrates a thorough and organized method for preparing teachers, which aligns with the most effective strategies in teacher education. One of the key strengths highlighted by the data is the emphasis on providing various learning experiences for teacher trainees. The survey findings indicate that every participant (100%) involves their trainees in peer teaching, assignment presentations, group discussions, and diverse evaluation methods (Korthagen, 2010). This multifaceted approach is crucial for developing well-rounded teaching skills, as it exposes the trainees to diverse instructional methodologies and allows them to practice their skills in different contexts (Darling-Hammond & Bransford, 2007; Korthagen, 2014).

The data also underscores the importance of feedback and reflection within teacher training programs. All respondents (100%) reported asking their trainees to provide corrective feedback and engage in self-reflection or peer reflection after each teaching activity (Schön, 1983). Focusing on continuous feedback and reflective practice enables the trainees to identify their strengths, address their weaknesses, and improve their teaching skills (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 1999).

Furthermore, the survey findings emphasize providing teacher trainees ample hands-on practice and observation opportunities. All respondents (100%) reported that they offered their trainees the chance to prepare and deliver peer-teaching lessons and conduct lesson demonstrations for the trainees (Lamb, 2015; Stigmar, 2016). This practical experience is crucial for bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and its practical implementation, instilling confidence in the reader about the effectiveness of the training (Kavanoz & Yüksel, 2010; Ten Cate & Durning, 2007). It allows trainees to use their material in real-world situations and improve their teaching skills (Herrington & Herrington, 2006; Lowell & Moore, 2020; Wati et al., 2020). The data also reveals that the respondents prioritize the development of the trainees' confidence and leadership skills, with a high percentage (94.44%) selecting confident teacher trainees to demonstrate lessons. This focus on building the trainees' self-assurance and leadership abilities is essential for their success in the classroom, as confident and competent teachers are more likely to engage their students and foster a positive

learning environment (Bandura, 1997; Billingsley et al., 2020; Zumbrunn et al., 2014). The poll results suggest that teacher training should implement a comprehensive and equitable approach, emphasizing diverse learning opportunities, continuous feedback and self-assessment, hands-on experience, and developing confidence and leadership skills. These practices align with the current best practices in teacher education and are likely to produce highly effective and confident teachers (Darling-Hammond, 2006).

The survey results offer valuable insights into the instructional approaches utilized by teacher educators when working with teacher trainees. The data demonstrates a thorough and organized method for preparing teachers, which aligns with the most effective strategies in teacher education. One of the key strengths highlighted by the data is the emphasis on providing various learning experiences for teacher trainees. The survey findings indicate that every participant (100%) involves their trainees in peer teaching, assignment presentations, group discussions, and diverse evaluation methods (Korthagen, 2010). This multifaceted approach is crucial for developing well-rounded teaching skills, as it exposes the trainees to diverse instructional methodologies and allows them to practice their skills in different contexts (Peffer & Renken, 2016; Thornhill-Miller et al., 2023; Zamiri & Esmaili, 2024).

The data also underscores the importance of feedback and reflection within teacher training programs. All respondents (100%) reported asking their trainees to provide corrective feedback and engage in self-reflection or peer reflection after each teaching activity (Schön, 2017). Focusing on continuous feedback and reflective practice enables the trainees to identify their strengths, address their weaknesses, and improve their teaching skills (Adler, 1991; Machost & Stains, 2023; Mohamed et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the survey findings emphasize providing teacher trainees ample hands-on practice and observation opportunities. All respondents (100%) reported that they offered their trainees the chance to prepare and deliver peer-teaching lessons and conduct lesson demonstrations for the trainees (Darling-Hammond, 2017). This practical experience is crucial for bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and its practical implementation, instilling confidence in the reader about the effectiveness of the training (Hashemiparast et al., 2019; Salifu et al., 2019). It allows trainees to use their material in real-world situations and improve their teaching skills (Fantinelli et al., 2024).

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The poll results suggest that teacher training should implement a comprehensive and equitable approach, emphasizing diverse learning opportunities, continuous feedback and self-assessment, hands-on experience, and developing confidence and leadership skills. These practices align with the current best practices in teacher education and are likely to produce highly effective and confident teachers (Darling-Hammond, 2006).

Conclusion

The findings of this survey provide valuable insights into the instructional practice teacher educators utilize in training future educators. The data indicates a well-

structured approach to teacher preparation that aligns with contemporary best practices, reinforcing the validity of the results. Critical strengths identified include providing diverse learning experiences, such as peer teaching and group discussions, which expose trainees to various instructional strategies and enhance their practical skills across different classroom settings. These diverse learning experiences not only broaden their knowledge but also reassure them of the quality of their training. Additionally, the significance of practical experience and observation is emphasized, enabling trainees to bridge theoretical knowledge with real-world application, thereby bolstering their confidence in their teaching abilities. The survey suggests that the teacher training programs assessed are effectively designed and implemented, offering a comprehensive preparation framework for aspiring educators. These findings serve as a valuable guide for the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sport in considering curriculum modifications to better meet teacher trainees' needs. Several recommendations are proposed to enhance further these programs: promoting ongoing professional development for educators, fostering collaborative relationships with local schools, improving feedback mechanisms, integrating technology into training, and promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion. Implementing these strategies can strengthen the effectiveness of teacher training programs, ultimately cultivating skilled and confident educators equipped to thrive in diverse educational environments.

Acknowledgment

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to all who contributed to this study. We extend our special thanks to our BTEC, PTEC, RTTC, PTTC administrators, and colleagues, whose invaluable survey allowance laid the foundation for our data analysis. We appreciate the collaborative support from our team's work and the resources provided by the institution's library and electronic trustful resources. Finally, we acknowledge the broader academic community for ongoing research on “Teacher Trainers’ Perception and Practice on Credit-Based Curriculum in English Language Teaching at Teacher Education College”.

Author Contributions

All the authors contributed to this research.

Funding

Not applicable.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethics Approval and Informed Consent Statement

This study received ethical approval from the BTEC, PTEC, RTTC, and PTTC’s administrative on January 25th, 2023.

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